

* Encoding: UTF-8.

UNIANOVA Amp BY Repro Position

/METHOD=SSTYPE(3)

/INTERCEPT=INCLUDE

/POSTHOC=Repro Position(TUKEY)

/EMMEANS=TABLES(Repro*Position) COMPARE(Repro) ADJ(LSD)

/EMMEANS=TABLES(Repro*Position) COMPARE(Position) ADJ(LSD)

/PRINT DESCRIPTIVE

/CRITERIA=ALPHA(.05)

/DESIGN=Repro Position Repro*Position.

Univariate Analysis of Variance

Notes

Output Created		14-JUL-2024 17:01:00
Comments		
Input	Data	D: \gits\diss\plotting\loudness \SPSS\VersuchsErgebnisse.sav
	Active Dataset	DataSet2
	Filter	<none>
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	Split File	<none>
	N of Rows in Working Data File	240
Missing Value Handling	Definition of Missing	User-defined missing values are treated as missing.
	Cases Used	Statistics are based on all cases with valid data for all variables in the model.

Notes

Syntax		UNIANOVA Amp BY Repr Position /METHOD=SSTYPE(3) /INTERCEPT=INCLUDE /POSTHOC=Repr Position(TUKEY) /EMMEANS=TABLES (Repr*Position) COMPARE(Repr) ADJ (LSD) /EMMEANS=TABLES (Repr*Position) COMPARE(Position) ADJ (LSD) /PRINT DESCRIPTIVE /CRITERIA=ALPHA(.05) /DESIGN=Repr Position Repr*Position.
Resources	Processor Time	00:00:00,03
	Elapsed Time	00:00:00,03

Between-Subjects Factors

		N
Repr	CTC	80
	HOA	80
	VBAP	80
Position	Pos1	60
	Pos2	60
	Pos3	60
	Pos4	60

Descriptive Statistics

Dependent Variable: Amp

Repro	Position	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
CTC	Pos1	-2.75590062	1.377882453	20
	Pos2	-.597249895	.9883323336	20
	Pos3	1.014138616	1.212921816	20
	Pos4	-.792575358	.8395346561	20
	Total	-.782896813	1.739738776	80
HOA	Pos1	-.128906145	.9187899399	20
	Pos2	.1961262250	.7120644267	20
	Pos3	2.977867826	1.066683277	20
	Pos4	.2284870390	.9424750029	20
	Total	.8183937363	1.551180120	80
VBAP	Pos1	-1.68628817	1.289699513	20
	Pos2	.1393205160	1.009966329	20
	Pos3	.6566764525	.9629793580	20
	Pos4	.2657805325	.3867989373	20
	Total	-.156127666	1.315883719	80
Total	Pos1	-1.52369831	1.613077910	60
	Pos2	-.087267718	.9690833139	60
	Pos3	1.549560965	1.482495152	60
	Pos4	-.099435929	.8976268607	60
	Total	-.040210248	1.674526520	240

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects

Dependent Variable: Amp

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	438.575 ^a	11	39.870	39.252	.000
Intercept	.388	1	.388	.382	.537
Repro	104.178	2	52.089	51.281	.000
Position	284.030	3	94.677	93.209	.000
Repro * Position	50.368	6	8.395	8.265	.000
Error	231.590	228	1.016		
Total	670.553	240			
Corrected Total	670.165	239			

a. R Squared = .654 (Adjusted R Squared = .638)

Estimated Marginal Means

1. Repro * Position

Estimates

Dependent Variable: Amp

Repro	Position	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
CTC	Pos1	-2.756	.225	-3.200	-2.312
	Pos2	-.597	.225	-1.041	-.153
	Pos3	1.014	.225	.570	1.458
	Pos4	-.793	.225	-1.237	-.349
HOA	Pos1	-.129	.225	-.573	.315
	Pos2	.196	.225	-.248	.640
	Pos3	2.978	.225	2.534	3.422
	Pos4	.228	.225	-.216	.673
VBAP	Pos1	-1.686	.225	-2.130	-1.242
	Pos2	.139	.225	-.305	.583
	Pos3	.657	.225	.213	1.101
	Pos4	.266	.225	-.178	.710

Pairwise Comparisons

Dependent Variable: Amp

Position	(I) Repro	(J) Repro	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval
						Lower Bound
Pos1	CTC	HOA	-2.627*	.319	.000	-3.255
		VBAP	-1.070*	.319	.001	-1.698
	HOA	CTC	2.627*	.319	.000	1.999
		VBAP	1.557*	.319	.000	.929
	VBAP	CTC	1.070*	.319	.001	.442
		HOA	-1.557*	.319	.000	-2.185
Pos2	CTC	HOA	-.793*	.319	.014	-1.421
		VBAP	-.737*	.319	.022	-1.365
	HOA	CTC	.793*	.319	.014	.165
		VBAP	.057	.319	.859	-.571
	VBAP	CTC	.737*	.319	.022	.109
		HOA	-.057	.319	.859	-.685
Pos3	CTC	HOA	-1.964*	.319	.000	-2.592
		VBAP	.357	.319	.263	-.271
	HOA	CTC	1.964*	.319	.000	1.336
		VBAP	2.321*	.319	.000	1.693

Pairwise Comparisons

Dependent Variable: Amp

Position	(I) Repro	(J) Repro	95% Confidence Interval for ^b ...
			Upper Bound
Pos1	CTC	HOA	-1.999
		VBAP	-.442
	HOA	CTC	3.255
		VBAP	2.185
Pos2	CTC	HOA	-.165
		VBAP	-.109
	HOA	CTC	1.421
		VBAP	.685
Pos3	CTC	HOA	-1.336
		VBAP	.985
	HOA	CTC	2.592
		VBAP	2.949

Pairwise Comparisons

Dependent Variable: Amp

Position	(I) Repro	(J) Repro	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence ^b ...
						Lower Bound
	VBAP	CTC	-.357	.319	.263	-.985
		HOA	-2.321*	.319	.000	-2.949
Pos4	CTC	HOA	-1.021*	.319	.002	-1.649
		VBAP	-1.058*	.319	.001	-1.686
	HOA	CTC	1.021*	.319	.002	.393
		VBAP	-.037	.319	.907	-.665
	VBAP	CTC	1.058*	.319	.001	.430
		HOA	.037	.319	.907	-.591

Pairwise Comparisons

Dependent Variable: Amp

Position	(I) Repro	(J) Repro	95% Confidence Interval for ^{b.}
			Upper Bound
	VBAP	CTC	.271
		HOA	-1.693
Pos4	CTC	HOA	-.393
		VBAP	-.430
	HOA	CTC	1.649
		VBAP	.591
	VBAP	CTC	1.686
		HOA	.665

Based on estimated marginal means

*. The mean difference is significant at the .05 level.

b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Least Significant Difference (equivalent to no adjustments).

Univariate Tests

Dependent Variable: Amp

Position		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Pos1	Contrast	69.804	2	34.902	34.361	.000
	Error	231.590	228	1.016		
Pos2	Contrast	7.835	2	3.917	3.857	.023
	Error	231.590	228	1.016		
Pos3	Contrast	62.480	2	31.240	30.756	.000
	Error	231.590	228	1.016		
Pos4	Contrast	14.427	2	7.214	7.102	.001
	Error	231.590	228	1.016		

Each F tests the simple effects of Repro within each level combination of the other effects shown. These tests are based on the linearly independent pairwise comparisons among the estimated marginal means.

2. Repro * Position

Estimates

Dependent Variable: Amp

Repro	Position	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
CTC	Pos1	-2.756	.225	-3.200	-2.312
	Pos2	-.597	.225	-1.041	-.153
	Pos3	1.014	.225	.570	1.458
	Pos4	-.793	.225	-1.237	-.349
HOA	Pos1	-.129	.225	-.573	.315
	Pos2	.196	.225	-.248	.640
	Pos3	2.978	.225	2.534	3.422
	Pos4	.228	.225	-.216	.673
VBAP	Pos1	-1.686	.225	-2.130	-1.242
	Pos2	.139	.225	-.305	.583
	Pos3	.657	.225	.213	1.101
	Pos4	.266	.225	-.178	.710

Pairwise Comparisons

Dependent Variable: Amp

Repro	(I) Position	(J) Position	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence b...
						Lower Bound
CTC	Pos1	Pos2	-2.159*	.319	.000	-2.787
		Pos3	-3.770*	.319	.000	-4.398
		Pos4	-1.963*	.319	.000	-2.591
	Pos2	Pos1	2.159*	.319	.000	1.531
		Pos3	-1.611*	.319	.000	-2.239
		Pos4	.195	.319	.541	-.433
	Pos3	Pos1	3.770*	.319	.000	3.142
		Pos2	1.611*	.319	.000	.983
		Pos4	1.807*	.319	.000	1.179
	Pos4	Pos1	1.963*	.319	.000	1.335
		Pos2	-.195	.319	.541	-.823
		Pos3	-1.807*	.319	.000	-2.435
HOA	Pos1	Pos2	-.325	.319	.309	-.953
		Pos3	-3.107*	.319	.000	-3.735
		Pos4	-.357	.319	.263	-.985

Pairwise Comparisons

Dependent Variable: Amp

Repro	(I) Position	(J) Position	95% Confidence Interval for ^b ...
			Upper Bound
CTC	Pos1	Pos2	-1.531
		Pos3	-3.142
		Pos4	-1.335
	Pos2	Pos1	2.787
		Pos3	-.983
		Pos4	.823
	Pos3	Pos1	4.398
		Pos2	2.239
		Pos4	2.435
	Pos4	Pos1	2.591
		Pos2	.433
		Pos3	-1.179
HOA	Pos1	Pos2	.303
		Pos3	-2.479
		Pos4	.271

Pairwise Comparisons

Dependent Variable: Amp

Repro	(I) Position	(J) Position	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence b...
						Lower Bound
VBAP	Pos2	Pos1	.325	.319	.309	-.303
		Pos3	-2.782*	.319	.000	-3.410
		Pos4	-.032	.319	.919	-.660
	Pos3	Pos1	3.107*	.319	.000	2.479
		Pos2	2.782*	.319	.000	2.154
		Pos4	2.749*	.319	.000	2.121
	Pos4	Pos1	.357	.319	.263	-.271
		Pos2	.032	.319	.919	-.596
		Pos3	-2.749*	.319	.000	-3.377
VBAP	Pos1	Pos2	-1.826*	.319	.000	-2.454
		Pos3	-2.343*	.319	.000	-2.971
		Pos4	-1.952*	.319	.000	-2.580
	Pos2	Pos1	1.826*	.319	.000	1.198
		Pos3	-.517	.319	.106	-1.145
		Pos4	-.126	.319	.692	-.754
	Pos3	Pos1	2.343*	.319	.000	1.715
		Pos2	.517	.319	.106	-.111
		Pos4	.391	.319	.221	-.237
	Pos4	Pos1	1.952*	.319	.000	1.324
		Pos2	.126	.319	.692	-.502
		Pos3	-.391	.319	.221	-1.019

Pairwise Comparisons

Dependent Variable: Amp

Repro	(I) Position	(J) Position	95% Confidence Interval for ... ^b
			Upper Bound
VBAP	Pos2	Pos1	.953
		Pos3	-2.154
		Pos4	.596
	Pos3	Pos1	3.735
		Pos2	3.410
		Pos4	3.377
	Pos4	Pos1	.985
		Pos2	.660
		Pos3	-2.121
VBAP	Pos1	Pos2	-1.198
		Pos3	-1.715
		Pos4	-1.324
	Pos2	Pos1	2.454
		Pos3	.111
		Pos4	.502
	Pos3	Pos1	2.971
		Pos2	1.145
		Pos4	1.019
	Pos4	Pos1	2.580
		Pos2	.754
		Pos3	.237

Based on estimated marginal means

*. The mean difference is significant at the .05 level.

b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Least Significant Difference (equivalent to no adjustments).

Univariate Tests

Dependent Variable: Amp

Repro		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
CTC	Contrast	143.133	3	47.711	46.971	.000
	Error	231.590	228	1.016		
HOA	Contrast	125.918	3	41.973	41.322	.000
	Error	231.590	228	1.016		
VBAP	Contrast	65.347	3	21.782	21.445	.000
	Error	231.590	228	1.016		

Each F tests the simple effects of Position within each level combination of the other effects shown. These tests are based on the linearly independent pairwise comparisons among the estimated marginal means.

Post Hoc Tests

Repro

Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: Amp

Tukey HSD

(I) Repro	(J) Repro	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
CTC	HOA	-1.60129055*	.1593537806	.000	-1.97722569	-1.22535541
	VBAP	-.626769147*	.1593537806	.000	-1.00270429	-.250834004
HOA	CTC	1.60129055*	.1593537806	.000	1.225355406	1.977225693
	VBAP	.974521402*	.1593537806	.000	.5985862590	1.350456546
VBAP	CTC	.626769147*	.1593537806	.000	.2508340039	1.002704290
	HOA	-.974521402*	.1593537806	.000	-1.35045655	-.598586259

Based on observed means.

The error term is Mean Square(Error) = 1.016.

*. The mean difference is significant at the .05 level.

Homogeneous Subsets

Amp

Tukey HSD^{a,b}

Repro	N	Subset		
		1	2	3
CTC	80	-.782896813		
VBAP	80		-.156127666	
HOA	80			.8183937363
Sig.		1.000	1.000	1.000

Means for groups in homogeneous subsets are displayed.

Based on observed means.

The error term is Mean Square(Error) = 1.016.

a. Uses Harmonic Mean Sample Size = 80.000.

b. Alpha = .05.

Position

Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: Amp

Tukey HSD

(I) Position	(J) Position	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% ...
					Lower Bound
Pos1	Pos2	-1.43643059 [*]	.1840058963	.000	-1.91265224
	Pos3	-3.07325927 [*]	.1840058963	.000	-3.54948092
	Pos4	-1.42426238 [*]	.1840058963	.000	-1.90048403
Pos2	Pos1	1.43643059 [*]	.1840058963	.000	.9602089417
	Pos3	-1.63682868 [*]	.1840058963	.000	-2.11305033
	Pos4	.0121682110	.1840058963	1.000	-.464053438
Pos3	Pos1	3.07325927 [*]	.1840058963	.000	2.597037625
	Pos2	1.63682868 [*]	.1840058963	.000	1.160607034
	Pos4	1.64899689 [*]	.1840058963	.000	1.172775245
Pos4	Pos1	1.42426238 [*]	.1840058963	.000	.9480407307
	Pos2	-.012168211	.1840058963	1.000	-.488389860
	Pos3	-1.64899689 [*]	.1840058963	.000	-2.12521854

Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: Amp

Tukey HSD

95% Confidence ..

(I) Position	(J) Position	Upper Bound
Pos1	Pos2	-.960208942
	Pos3	-2.59703762
	Pos4	-.948040731
Pos2	Pos1	1.912652239
	Pos3	-1.16060703
	Pos4	.4883898596
Pos3	Pos1	3.549480922
	Pos2	2.113050331
	Pos4	2.125218542
Pos4	Pos1	1.900484028
	Pos2	.4640534376
	Pos3	-1.17277525

Based on observed means.

The error term is Mean Square(Error) = 1.016.

*. The mean difference is significant at the .05 level.

Homogeneous Subsets

Amp

Tukey HSD^{a,b}

Position	N	Subset		
		1	2	3
Pos1	60	-1.52369831		
Pos4	60		-.099435929	
Pos2	60		-.087267718	
Pos3	60			1.549560965
Sig.		1.000	1.000	1.000

Means for groups in homogeneous subsets are displayed.

Based on observed means.

The error term is Mean Square(Error) = 1.016.

a. Uses Harmonic Mean Sample Size = 60.000.

b. Alpha = .05.